

impact on days to maturity in Mansarover, but showed a marked effect on maturity period in C14-8 when applied at later growth stages, mainly because of a delay in maturity

of nodal panicles. It is clear from the results that active tillering was the most N-responsive growth stage in high-yielding Mansarover, whereas the

reproductive and flowering stages were found to be the most N-effective growth stages in traditional variety C14-8. ■

Crop management

Lock-lodge technology for rice ratooning

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Ratooning of rice could be an important crop establishment alternative in many agroecosystems. But low yield potential and asynchronous grain ripening constrain the widescale use of ratooning in the tropics. Braiding and lodging (lock-lodge method) the stubbles after harvest of the main crop can overcome these limitations considerably.

We tested the ratoon performance of varieties IR20, ADT38, CO 43, and Ponni in an experiment conducted at

Grain yield and duration of main and ratoon rice varieties.

Variety	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Duration (d)		
	Conventional ratoon	Lock-lodge ratoon	Main crop	Conventional ratoon	Lock-lodge ratoon	Main crop
IR20	1.4 (41.1)	2.9 (82.7)	3.5	62	95	117
CO 43	1.7 (38.9)	3.1 (70.8)	4.4	97	97	140
ADT38	1.3 (23.7)	3.0 (55.2)	5.4	79	105	133
Ponni	1.5 (26.1)	2.4 (41.2)	5.9	71	97	140

Numbers in parentheses indicate the percentage grain yield when compared with the respective main crop.

Tamil Nadu Agricultural University in Coimbatore in 1993-94 using both conventional and lock-lodge methods of ratooning. Results showed that lock-lodge ratooning consistently out-yielded the conventional method irrespective of variety. All the traits of the ratoon crop measured were significantly better in the lock-lodge

ratoon crop. Grain yield of lock-lodge ratoon crop increased by 41.2% for Ponni to 82.7% for IR20 compared with their respective main crop (see table). Growth duration of lock-lodge ratoon ranged from 95 to 105 d, whereas that of conventional ratoon ranged from 62 to 97 d depending on variety. ■

Disease management

Soil-borne and seed-borne pathogens of rice in rice - wheat system-based farmers' fields in Uttar Pradesh

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Pests (insects, weeds, pathogens) are an important component for sustaining rice - wheat systems. Among them, soil- and seed-borne pathogens may play a specific role. Cropping practices may affect the dynamics of these pathogens, both in their survival and epidemic phases. More specifically, the carryover role of other crops in rotation with rice may be critical for these

diseases. Pathogen interactions may also alter disease patterns in a field. These interactions remain largely unknown, and we report here some preliminary results on this topic.

Disease incidence due to a few soil- and seed-borne pathogens was quantified in farmers' fields for sheath blight (ShB, *Rhizoctonia solani*), stem rot (SR, *Sclerotium oryzae*), brown spot (BS, *Cochliobolus miyabeanus*), sheath rot (ShR, *Sarocladium oryzae*), panicle blast (PB, *Pyricularia grisea*), crown sheath rot (CShR, *Gaeumannomyces graminis*), and false smut (FS, *Ustilaginoidea virens*). These diseases can be transmitted by seeds (BS, ShR, PB, CShR) or survive as propagules in the soil or in plant debris (ShB, SR, BS, PB, CShR, FS) (Ou 1985). Glume discoloration (GD) symptoms were also considered because they are

associated with the presence of different fungi, such as *P. grisea* and *C. miyabeanus*. Eight fields selected to represent a range of crops preceding rice were assessed: two with wheat (B3 and B6), one with rice (B4), one with sorghum (B1), one with maize (PP5), one with lentil (B9), one with fallow (PP2), and one with mint (PP3).

Diseases were assessed at the milk stage. In each field, 20 hills were sampled following a zigzag pattern. For each hill, the total number of tillers; number of tillers infected by ShB, SR, BS, and CShR; total number of panicles; number of panicles infected by ShR, PB, and FS; and number of panicles showing GD were recorded. Sheath blight, stem rot, brown spot, glume discoloration, and sheath rot were consistently observed in all eight